

Handling Mobility in WiMAX

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Abstract: World Wide Interoperability for Microwave Access (WiMAX) is a telecommunications technology aimed to providing wireless data over wider coverage area in a variety of ways, from point to point links to full mobile cellular type access. It is based on IEEE Std. 802.16 attempts to bring quality of services, high data rates and coverage to wireless computer networks. Mobility of wireless communication is increase with wireless MAN standard 802.16. The attractive feature of WiMAX for wireless communication is mobility among homogeneous networks and heterogeneous network. Homogeneous mobility is the moving of MS between the networks of same technology. In Heterogeneous mobility MS is moving between the different network such as mobility handling between Wi-fi and WiMAX. In this paper we discuss both heterogeneous and homogeneous networks with respect to mobility handling for 802.16. In this paper we review the various approaches for achieving mobility in WiMAX network.

Keywords- Mobility Management, WiMAX, handover, Wi-Fi, Homogeneous and Heterogeneous networks.

1. INTRODUCTION

There are different modes in communication technology like wired, wireless, adhoc, mobile. The growth of communication technology is tremendous. The requirements of customer also goes on increasing. The technology which is use for communication today becomes outdated for tomorrows communication requirements. So it is necessary to satisfy their requirements. Provide uninterrupted communication to customer the different technologies are integrate with each other. For the success of WiMAX technology it is necessary to integrate with other networks and handling mobility with them. The mobility handling for WiMAX in both homogeneous and heterogeneous environment is important. The latter enables users to maintain their application session while moving within a single or among several access technologies.

The IEEE 802.11 wireless local area network (WLAN) technologies or Wi-fi are widely deployed and well suited for

home and small office environments. The latest development in Wi-fi is IEEE 802.11n, reaches a maximum data rate of 600 Mbps. WLANs are cheap to install and operate; however, their coverage area is limited to hundreds of meters only, and mobility support is minimal.

The IEEE 802.16 family of standards for Wireless Metropolitan Area Networks has been named as WiMAX by the WiMAX Forum [1]. They call WiMAX a standard-based technology enabling the delivery of last mile wireless broadband access as an alternative to cable and DSL. The ongoing evolution of IEEE 802.16 will expand the standard to address mobile applications thus enabling broadband access directly to WiMAX enabled portable devices ranging from smart phones and Pads to notebook and laptop computers. It offers broadband wireless access that is capable of providing mobile users with quality of service (QoS) support as detailed in the latest amendment, IEEE 802.16e [1].

The WiMAX can be provided the many features such as the flexible architecture, High security, mobility, Quick Deployment, Portability, Multi level services, Cost effective, wider coverage, High capacity, Scalability, NON-Line-of-Sight operation and Interoperability [5].

The WiMAX family of standards concentrates on two types of usage models a fixed usage model and a mobile usage model. The basic element that differentiates these systems is the ground speed at which the systems are designed to manage. Based on mobility management, wireless access systems are designed to operate on the move without any disturbance of any service. Wireless access can be divided into three classes given as stationary, pedestrian and vehicular. A mobile wireless access system is one that can address the vehicular class, where as the fixed serves the stationary and pedestrian classes.

In order to provide ubiquitous availability of multimedia services and applications, wireless and mobile technologies are evolving towards integration of heterogeneous access networks such as wireless personal area networks (WPANs), Wi-fi, WiMax as well as third-generation (3G). The integration of these networks will benefit for both users and service providers. Users will benefit from the performance of expanded network coverage and greater data transmission speeds. Economically, service providers will receive a better

return on their investment because of the larger number of users because this technology covers a greater area and provides better services

In this paper we constrained our work to mobility feature of WiMAX. Mobility management is achieved with handover mechanism of 802.16[8]. Paper is organized as follows, section 2 describes wireless technologies ,section 3 describes the handover mechanism, and section 4 describes the mobility in heterogeneous and homogeneous networks.

2. OVERVIEW

2.1 Wi-Fi:

IEEE 802.11 is also known as Wi-Fi which is an abbreviation for Wireless Fidelity and a catch all phrase for the several different standards and recommendations that comprise wireless networking. Wi-Fi (short for "Wireless Fidelity") is the popular term for a high-frequency wireless local area network (WLAN). WiFi allows APs a coverage radius, or hotspot, of approximately 100m in interior spaces [10]. Meanwhile, WiFi exterior coverage can cover a radius of approximately 300m, depending on environmental conditions. The transmission speed of the different WiFi standards ranges from 11Mbps until 54Mbps [10].

WiFi's advantages include:

- Its use of a non-licensed frequency band.
- Its fewer international regulatory restrictions.
- Its architecture that allows for ubiquitous functioning and dynamic growth.
- Its low cost.
- Its mobility without network connection breaks.

WiFi's disadvantages include:

- Its use of the 2.4GHz spectrum, which is susceptible to interference.
- Its higher energy consumption when compared to other standards.

2.2 WiMax:

WiMAX is a standards-based technology enabling the delivery of last mile wireless broadband access as an alternative to wired broadband like cable and DSL. WiMAX provides fixed, nomadic, portable and, soon, mobile wireless broadband connectivity without the need for direct line-of-sight with a base station. In a typical cell radius deployment of three to ten kilometers, WiMAX Forum Certified systems can be expected to deliver capacity of up to 40 Mbps per channel, for fixed and portable access applications. WiMax is a telecommunications technology aimed at providing wireless data over long distances in a variety of ways, from point-to-point links to full mobile cellular type access. It is based on the IEEE 802.16 standard, which is also called Wireless MAN. The name "WiMax" was created by the WiMax Forum, which was formed in June 2001 to promote conformance and

interoperability of the standard. To serve the demand for access to the internet "any where any time" and ensure quality of service, the IEEE 802.16 working group brought out a new broadband wireless access technology called "WiMax" meaning Worldwide Interoperability for Microwave Access. It was introduced by the IEEE 802.16 working group to facilitate broadband services on areas where cable infrastructure is inadequate.

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In many parts of the world, existing fixed-line carriers that do not own cellular, PCS, or 3G spectrums could turn to WiMax for provisioning mobility services. As the industry moves along the path of quadruple-play service bundles—voice, data, video, and mobility some service providers that do not have a mobility component in their portfolios—cable operators, satellite companies, and incumbent phone companies—are likely to find WiMax attractive. For many of these companies, having a mobility plan will be not only a new revenue opportunity but also a defensive play to mitigate churn by enhancing the value of their product set. Existing mobile operators are less likely to adopt WiMax and more likely to continue along the path of 3G evolution for higher data rate capabilities. There may be scenarios, however, in which traditional mobile operators may deploy WiMax as an overlay solution to provide even higher data rates in targeted urban centers or metro zones. In addition to higher-speed Internet access, mobile WiMax can be used to provide voiceover- IP services in the future. The low-latency design of mobile WiMax makes it possible to deliver VoIP services effectively. VoIP technologies may also be leveraged to provide innovative new services, such as voice chatting, push-to-talk, and multimedia chatting. New and existing operators may also attempt to use WiMax to offer differentiated personal broadband services, such as mobile entertainment. The flexible channel bandwidths and multiple levels of quality-of-service (QoS) support may allow WiMax to be used by service providers for differentiated high-bandwidth and low-latency entertainment applications.

Some important characteristics of WiMAX include:

- Its use of the microwave frequency band for wireless data transmission.

- Its high transmission speed over long distances.
- Its use of OFDM (Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing) to enable non-line-of sight communication.
- Its multi-channel support for TDD (Time Division Duplex) and FDD (Frequency Division Duplex)
- Its flexible handling of channels in the 3.5MHz, 5MHz and 10MHz frequencies.

Some challenges for WiMAX include:

- Reaching a coverage area of up to 10 miles.
- Providing wireless broadband and dedicated links.
- Making the technology more affordable.
- Allowing access from more remote areas.

The WiMax standard has been developed with many objectives in mind. These are Summarized below:

- Flexible Architecture: WiMax supports several system architectures, including Point-to-Point, Point-to-Multipoint, and ubiquitous coverage. The WiMax MAC (Media Access Control) supports Point-to-Multipoint and ubiquitous service by scheduling a time slot for each Subscriber Station (SS). If there is only one SS in the network, the WiMax Base Station (BS) will communicate with the SS on a Point-to-Point basis. A BS in a Point-to-Point configuration may use a narrower beam antenna to cover longer distances.
- High Security: WiMax supports AES (Advanced Encryption Standard) and 3DES(Triple DES, where DES is the Data Encryption Standard). By encrypting the links between the BS and the SS, WiMax provides subscribers with privacy and security across the broadband wireless interface. Security also provides operators with strong protection against theft of service. WiMax also has built-in VLAN support, which provides protection for data that is being transmitted by different users on the same BS.
- Quick Deployment: Compared with the deployment of wired solutions, WiMax requires little or no external plant construction. For example, excavation to support the trenching of cables is not required. Operators that have obtained licenses to use one of the licensed bands, or that plan to use one of the unlicensed bands, do not need to submit further applications to the Government. Once the antenna and equipment are installed and powered, WiMax is ready for service. In most cases, deployment of WiMax can be completed in a matter of hours, compared with months for other solutions.
- Multi Level Service: The manner in which QoS is delivered is generally based on the Service Level Agreement (SLA) between the service provider and the end-user. Further, one service provider can offer different SLA s to different subscribers, or even to different users on the same SS.
- Interoperability: WiMax is based on international, vendor-neutral standards, which make it easier for end-users to

transport and use their SS at different locations, or with different service providers. Interoperability protects the early investment of an operator since it can select equipment from different equipment vendors, and it will continue to drive the costs of equipment down as a result of mass adoption.

- Portability: WiMax is based on international, vendor-neutral standards, which make it easier for end-users to transport and use their SS at different locations, or with different service providers. Interoperability protects the early investment of an operator since it can select equipment from different equipment vendors, and it will continue to drive the costs of equipment down as a result of mass adoption.
- Mobility: The IEEE 802.16e amendment has added key features in support of mobility. Improvements have been made to the OFDM and OFDMA physical layers to support devices and services in a mobile environment. These improvements, which include Scalable OFDMA, MIMO, and support for idle/sleep mode and hand-off, will allow full mobility at speeds up to 160 km/hr.
- Cost effective: : WiMax is based on an open, international standard. Mass adoption of the standard, and the use of low-cost, mass-produced chipsets, will drive costs down dramatically, and the resultant competitive pricing will provide considerable cost savings for service providers and end-users.
- Wider coverage area: WiMax systems are able to cover a large geographic area when the path between the BS and the SS is unobstructed.
- High Capacity: Using higher modulation (64-QAM) and channel bandwidth(currently 7 MHz, with planned evolution towards the full bandwidth specified in the standards), WiMax systems can provide significant capacity.
- Scalability: Despite an increasingly globalize economy, spectrum resources for wireless broadband worldwide are still quite disparate in its allocations. Mobile WiMax technology therefore, is designed to be able to scale to work in from 1.25 to 20 MHz.
- Non Line of sight operation: NLOS usually refers to a radio path with its first Fresnel zone completely blocked. WiMax is based on OFDM technology, which has the inherent capability of handling NLOS environments. This capability helps WiMax products deliver broad bandwidth in a NLOS, which other wireless product cannot do.

3. HANDOVER

Handover is the means of maintaining a call when a user moves outside the coverage area of the serving cell. The call must be switched to an alternative cell to provide service, automatically and without loss of service.

Handover is a very complex process requiring synchronisation of events between the mobile station or serving cell and the network. There is the need to route the call

to the new cell before handoff can be affected while maintaining the old connection until the new connection is known to have succeeded. The goal of handover procedure is to maintain the mobile terminals' connections as they continue to move and change their base stations. When the term handover is used the basic concept which comes to mind is, to provide the continuous connectivity to the MS when it shifts from coverage area of one BS to other BS. Handover is a time critical process requiring action to be taken before the existing network link degrades to such an extent that the call is lost. Handover is the process of changing the network associated with the current connection while a call is in progress. It is often initiated either by crossing a cell boundary or by deterioration in quality of the signal in the current network.

In cellular telecommunications, the term handover refers to the process of transferring an ongoing call or data session from one channel connected to the core network to another. There may be different reasons why a handover might be conducted:

- When the phone is moving away from the area covered by one cell and entering the area covered by another cell the call is transferred to the second cell in order to avoid call termination when the phone gets outside the range of the first cell.
- When the capacity for connecting new calls of a given cell is used up and an existing or new call from a phone, which is located in an area overlapped by another cell, is transferred to that cell in order to free-up some capacity in the first cell for other users, who can only be connected to that cell;
- In non-CDMA networks when the channel used by the phone becomes interfered with by another phone using the same channel in a different cell, the call is transferred to a different channel in the same cell or to a different channel in another cell in order to avoid the interference.
- Again in non-CDMA networks when the user behavior changes, e.g. when a fast-travelling user, connected to a large, umbrella-type of cell, stops then the call may be transferred to a smaller macro-cell or even to a micro-cell in order to free capacity on the umbrella cell for other fast travelling users and to reduce the potential interference to other cells or users (this works in reverse too, when a user is detected to be moving faster than a certain threshold, the call can be transferred to a larger umbrella-type of cell in order to minimize the frequency of the handovers due to this movement);
- In CDMA networks a soft handover may be induced in order to reduce the interference to a smaller neighboring cell due to the "near-far" effect even when the phone still has an excellent connection to its current cell.

Usually a handover is understood as a change of physical connection point through which the terminal communicates with network services. In WiMAX this is called inter-cell handover. There exists also so called intra-cell handover which basically means changing from one frequency

to another while the serving BS remains the same. From wide perspective handovers may be split into two groups: horizontal HO and vertical HO. horizontal HO network technology remains the same, whereas the latter is an inter technology HO type There are different handover triggering ways. One natural method is based on signal level measurements. If the received signal level from the serving BS is deteriorated enough, resulting in better signal quality from one or more neighboring BSs, then it is reasonable to perform a HO. This method is also used in the simulations later in this document. Depending on the network characteristics and properties there might exist several other reasons for HO initiation, interference from other cells, fluctuating MS conditions and another network type offering a better performance. Handover initiation could be classified into four categories: Area-Based Scheme, Power-Measurement Scheme, Traffic-Based Scheme, Mobility-Based Scheme.

- Area-Based Scheme: In this scheme, a handover activity is initiated whenever the corresponding mobile terminal it enters into a handover area. The handover area is the area served by more than one base station.
- Power-Measurement Scheme: This scheme is an improvement of area-based strategy. In this scheme, the system or a mobile terminal detects the need for handover according to its received signal strength (RSS). If the RSS is below a minimum threshold level, or it perceives the existence of another base station that can provide a higher RSS, the corresponding handover activity initiates.
- Traffic-Based Scheme: In this scheme, each mobile terminal is assumed to possess the ability of perceiving the traffic load of the new cell. This scheme adopts the power-measure scheme to detect the need of handover; however, the mobile terminal may not handover to the new cell if the traffic load there is heavy.
- Mobility-Based Scheme: In this scheme, the system or a mobile terminal initiates a handover requires if they agree that the mobile terminal has high enough probability to enter into another cell with a given time interval. In this scheme, location prediction mechanism is required. Either the system or the mobile terminal is in charge to make the related predictions.

3.1 Types of handover:

A handover can be divided into two parts, the pre-registration phase and the actual handover. The pre-registration phase includes messages such as a handover request and a list of possible target BSs. During this phase the MS can also measure the signal strength from adjacent BSs to help in the decision about which BS to use as target BS. When the actual handover takes place the mobile station will close the connection to the serving BS and open a new to the target BS.

There are two different kinds of handovers and they differ in the way they handle the connections to serving and

target BS in the actual handover phase. The two types are hard and soft handover.

Hard handover is essentially a “break before make” connection. Under the control of the MSC (Mobile Switching Centre), the BS hands over the MSS’s call to another cell and then drop the call. In a hard handover, the link to the prior BS is terminated before or as the user is transferred to the new cell’s BS; the MSS is linked to no more than one BS at any given time. An advantage of the hard handover is that at any moment in time one call uses only one channel. The hard handover event is indeed very short and usually is not perceptible by the user. In the old analog systems it could be heard as a click or a very short beep, in digital systems it is unnoticeable. Another advantage of the hard handover is that the phone’s hardware does not need to be capable of receiving two or more channels in parallel, which makes it cheaper and simpler. A disadvantage is that if a handover fails the call may be temporarily disrupted or even terminated abnormally. Technologies, which utilize hard handovers, usually have procedures which can re-establish the connection to the source cell if the connection to the target cell cannot be made.

WiMax specification defines three types of handovers: Hard HO (HHO), FBSS (Fast Base Station Switching) and MDHO (Macro Diversity Handover) [3].

- Hard handover: It takes place when the signal strength of neighboring BS becomes stronger than the serving BS. MS communicates with only one BS at the same time so there may be brake-before-make.
- Macro diversity handover (MDHO): The situation where number of receivers and transmitters are used for transferring the same signal is called diversity. Macro diversity handover (MDHO) is an optional scheme to reduce the delay and packet loss during handover, since MS communicates with several BS all the BS involved are known as diversity set. Among number of BS in diversity set one BS which controls DL and UL allocations is referred as anchor BS. There might be some BS which are reachable by the MS but the signal is weak for traffic such BS are not included in the diversity set and falls under the category of neighbor BS. At some point neighbor BS can be included in diversity set when MS gets close to neighbor BS.
- Fast Base Station Switching (FBSS): Same as MDHO, It is also optional and maintains diversity set and anchor BS the purpose is same, to reduce the handover delay and packet loss. Serving BS which transmits and receives data from MS is anchor BS.

Fig 1 Types of Handover

Fig 2 WiMAX Reference model

4. MOBILITY IN WiMAX

The mobility handling in WiMax require to provide continuous connection or availability of network. Its effectively for rendering continuous service to mobile users in homogeneous and heterogeneous traffic through the estimation of resource requirements of potential handover connections.

To have an interoperable wireless network, simply MAC and PHY alone are not enough. The purpose is to deal with the aspects like IP connectivity, Qos, security and mobility management. End to end network aspects are developed and standardized by Network Working Group (NWG) of WiMax forum. Three stage development processes has been adopted by WiMax NWG for the development of end to end network architecture.

With the IEEE Std. 802.16 limiting itself to PHY and MAC-layer, the WiMAX Forum is developing a end-to-end network architecture specifying the access/core systems and its functionalities. It contains procedures and protocols for how the network will support e.g mobility, security, internetworking and authentication to a WiMAX subscriber station. A depiction of the network architecture is presented in the network reference model in fig 2. It contains entities such as (Mobile) Subscriber Stations ((M)SS), Access Service Network (ASN) and Connectivity Service Network (CSN).

The different types of handling mobility mention as follows:

4.1 Homogeneous Mobility

Homogeneous mobility is the moving of a MS between networks of the same technology. Homogeneous mobility is less complex then heterogeneous mobility since no other technologies or systems need to be considered when moving inside a homogeneous network. This mobility only requires support in the own network and this lead to less complicated solutions for roaming mechanisms since measurements like e.g. Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) can be utilized.

When the user moves with the cell phone it will most likely get out of range from the current BS and the system will perform an intra system (horizontal) handover. This transition between BSs is most often unnoticed by the user and this is where well developed horizontal handover procedures are important. If the system does not have well developed procedures for the handover the user will notice the interruption in the ongoing conversation.

The intra ASN handover is performed between BSs (or sectors within one BS) belonging to the same ASN. The BSs can be connected to the same ASN GW or different ASN GWs (within the same ASN) it will still be an intra ASN handover. An inter ASN handover is a handover between BSs not part of the same ASN. During an inter ASN handover ASN GWs in separate ASNs need to coordinate their actions to make the handover smooth to the MS.

In Homogeneous handover, an existing message has been chosen to serve as handover request and

acknowledgment. The MS will send this message to the BS when it wishes to perform a handover and the BS will respond with the same message. The message chosen does not affect either of the MS or BS if they do not have the mobility functionality, it simply tells the receiver to carry on as usual.

4.2 Heterogeneous Mobility

Heterogeneous mobility is inter-networking between two different network technologies. The difference in those technologies regarding QoS, range and data rates has formed a void in the topology of network technology. The different technology having users are mobile but still requires either a persistent connection or high data rates, and all of these with ubiquitous movement between the different technologies.

The customer increase of 3G devices and Wi-Fi market development is reason enough to investigate the inter-communication of WiMAX with these technologies, as telecommunication providers aim to protect their investments and extend customer services through new types of media.

We are discussing the mobility handling between Wi-fi and WiMAX. WiMax operates on the same general principles as Wi-Fi, it sends data from one computer to another via radio signals. A computer equipped with WiMax would receive data from the WiMax transmitting station, probably using encrypted data keys to prevent unauthorized users from stealing access.

WiMax is not designed to clash with Wi-Fi, but to coexist with it. WiMax coverage is measured in square kilometers, while that of Wi-Fi is measured in square meters. The original WiMax proposes the usage of 10-66 GHz frequency spectrum for the WiMax transmission, which is well above the Wi-Fi range (up to 5GHz). But 802.16a added support for 2-11 GHz frequency also. One WiMax base station can be accessed by more than 60 users. WiMax can also provide broadcasting services also.

Why we needed the mobility handling in Wi-fi and WiMAX. This need will be given as follows [9]:

- Providing fixed, portable and mobile broadband internet service
- Full range of services in the home, office as well as road.
- Providing both Frequency bands
- Provide a common user experience in either access networks
- Cost saving at both the silicon and device levels

There are some challenges in handling the mobility between Wi-Fi and WiMAX. These challenges are given as:

- Wireless standards: Wireless standards for different radio links tend to be a lot different such as Wi-Fi networks use management frames to do client addition and hand-off, while Wi-MAX networks use initial network entry procedure.

- Mobility parameter: Authentication and hand-off techniques differ across networks eg. latency
- Client complexity: Intelligent client software is required to allow roaming across different networks
- Network architecture: WiFi and WiMAX using different architecture, so it is hard to accommodate roaming and hand-over.

WiFi- WiMAX Technologies are integrated with each other. A WiFi/WiMAX gateway can connect the users of both technologies seamlessly[8]. In this case, the WiFi/WiMAX gateway implements both technologies, permitting users from one side to access services on other side. In other words, WiFi users can have access to WiMAX services that are not in their coverage area by employing the multi-hop characteristics of Mobile Ad Hoc Networks (MANET) networks. The integration or handling mobility in WiFi-WiMAX has become increasingly common in urban areas where they work in tandem to provide mobile services and a variety of applications. Presently, several cities are attempting to become “wireless cities” in an effort to provide broadband wireless internet access throughout their entire metropolitan areas. WiFi and WiMAX are two options for internet access in metropolitan networks[11]. Presently, integrating WiFi and Fixed WiMAX is the most practical way to deploy large-scale wireless networks in cities that require wireless broadband connectivity [11].

In Cisco system paper they given architecture [2] which handling mobility in Wi-Fi and WiMax. In this architecture with a common Wi-Fi/WiMAX mobility service agent for use across Wi-Fi and WiMAX access. In a WiMAX network, an Access Service network (ASN) gateway is a network element that provides mobility in conjunction with multiple WiMAX base stations. By incorporating a correct mapping mechanism between Wi-Fi and WiMAX, a Wi-Fi Access Point can also interface to the WiMAX ASNGW. This enables a Wi-Fi/WiMAX mobility service agent to be easily created using a ASN Gateway.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we studied Wimax network. The WiMAX technology and architecture form a complex, but feature-rich environment for supplying end user mobility. It shares many characteristics of cellular networks, such as architecture support of billing, mobility, and QoS, but also scales down with the technology being used for bridging other networks. Then We also mention the handover techniques and handover techniques in WiMax for integrate Wimax network with other networks.

In this paper, we have given the mobility handling in WiMAX with the help of homogeneous and heterogeneous networks. Both the networks have different configuration for supporting either 802.11 protocols or 802.16 protocols. WiMAX having a number of attractive features, but its

handover framework is somewhat complicated and having some drawbacks. A mobility scheme allowing seamless hand over across WiFi and WiMAX promises convenient broadband access solution by providing several advantages to both end-users and operators.

Research in this direction, handling mobility in different networks would also prove beneficial in a broader perspective since it will also address some of the issues in end-user transparent authentication.

In future work, we wish to give model as to handle mobility across heterogeneous networks in a broader perspective.

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